

Isocoumarins. Part II. Synthesis of some 3-Phenylisocoumarins

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Friedel-Crafts acylation of benzene, toluene, phenol, anisole, and phenetole with 4-methoxyhomophthalic anhydride in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$, and anhydrous $SnCl_4$ has been investigated. The reactions lead to the synthesis of some number of 7-methoxy-3-phenylisocoumarins.

Friedel-Crafts acylation of some aromatic hydrocarbons, phenols, and phenol ethers with homophthalic anhydride has been reported.¹ Acylation in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ has led to the formation of *o*-carboxybenzylphenyl ketone derivatives or a mixture of the ketones and *o*-benzoylphenylacetic acid derivatives. Sometimes the formation of 3-phenylisocoumarin derivative has also been observed.^{1b} The ketone derivatives have been cyclodehydrated to the corresponding 3-phenylisocoumarins either by heating to a high temperature or by heating with anhydrous $AlCl_3$.^{1b} Acylation of some phenols in presence of anhydrous $SnCl_4$ has also afforded 3-phenylisocoumarin derivatives directly.^{1c}

In the present investigation, the Friedel-Crafts acylation of benzene, toluene, phenol, anisole, and phenetole with 4-methoxyhomophthalic anhydride (I) has been studied in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ and anhydrous $SnCl_4$. With $AlCl_3$ the reaction was carried out at boiling water-bath temperature using nitrobenzene as solvent except in the case of benzene and toluene where instead of nitrobenzene excess of the hydrocarbon was used as solvent. Acylation in presence of anhydrous $SnCl_4$ was carried out at 120° without using any solvent.

Condensation of 4-methoxyhomophthalic anhydride (I) with benzene nucleus of the aromatic compounds can take place in two possible ways leading to formation of *o*-carboxybenzylphenyl ketone derivatives (II) and *o*-benzoylphenylacetic acid derivatives (III). In none of the reactions studied, the acids (III) were isolated under the conditions used. With anhydrous $AlCl_3$, the ketones (II) are generally formed and sometimes also the isocoumarins (IV). Anhydrous $SnCl_4$ was not effective in bringing out the condensation with benzene and toluene, but with phenol, anisole, and phenetole, it led to the formation of the isocoumarins (IVc-e) directly. The products obtained are shown in Table I.

1. (a) Graebe and Trumpp, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 375.
- (b) Shriner and Wnox, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1064.
- (c) Bau-Hoi, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1944, 398.
- (d) Horeau and Jaques, *ibid.*, 1948, 53.
- (e) Sorrie and Thomson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2244.
- (f) Legrand and Lozac'h, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1964, 1787.

(a : R = H; b : R = Me; c : R = OH; d : R = OMe; e : R = OEt.)

The ketones (IIa, IIb, and IId) were cyclodehydrated with 85% sulphuric acid to the corresponding isocoumarins (IVa, IVb, and IVe).

Treatment of the isocoumarins (IV,a-e) with hot aqueous NaOH solution opened the lactone ring and the respective ketones (II, a-e) formed were cyclised back with 85% sulphuric acid to the corresponding isocoumarins. The ketones (II a) and (II, b) were oxidised with alkaline hydrogen peroxide, whereas alkaline KMnO_4 was used for oxidation of the ketones (II, c-e). Benzoic acid, *p*-toluic acid, *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, *p*-anisic acid, and *p*-ethoxybenzoic together with 4-methoxyphthalic acid were isolated respectively from the oxidation of the ketones (II, a-e). This establishes the structure of the ketones and consequently of the isocoumarins.

TABLE I

Condensation of 4-methoxyhomophthalic anhydride with aromatic compounds

Aromatic Compounds	Anhydride (I) used	Condensing agent used	Solvent used	Product*	Cryst. form and shape	M.P. (Yield)	Analysis Percentage	
							Found.	Reqd.
Benzene (39 ml.)	3 g.	AlCl_3 (3.2 g.)	Nil	Ketone (IIa) $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$	Aq. ethanol; white shining plates	190-91° (2.3 g.)	C: 71.37 H: 5.2	71.12 5.2
Toluene (45 ml.)	3	AlCl_3 (3.2 g.)	Nil	Ketone (IIb) $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$	EtAc; white shining plates	215-16 (2.0 g.)	C: 72.0 H: 5.6	71.8 5.6
Phenol (0.9g.)	2	AlCl_3 (2.1 g.)	Nitrobenzene (12 ml.)	Isocoumarin (IVc) $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$	AcOH; pale green needles	223-24 (2.0g.)	C: 71.5 H: 4.9	71.6 4.5
Do	2	SnCl_4 (2.2 ml.)	Nil	Do	Do	223-24 (2.3 g.)		
Anisole (1.1 ml.)	2	AlCl_3 (2.1 g.)	Nitrobenzene (12 ml.)	Ketone (IId) $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$	Aq. ethanol; shining needles	178-79 (1.5 g.)	C: 68.3 H: 5.3	68.0 5.3
(0.56 ml.)	1	SnCl_4 (1.1 ml.)	Nil	Isocoumarin (IVd) $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$	Aq. ethanol; pale green needles	145-46 (1.0 g.)	C: 72.4 H: 4.9	72.3 4.9
Phenetole (1.3 ml.)	2	AlCl_3 (2.1 g.)	Nitrobenzene (12 ml.)	Isocoumarin (IVe) $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$	Do.	137-38 (1.6 g.)	H: 72.6 H: 5.5	72.9 5.4
(0.63 ml.)	1	SnCl_4 (1.2ml.)	Nil	Do	Do	137-138 (1.0g.)		

*2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl phenyl ketone (IIa); 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl-4-methylphenyl ketone (IIb); 7-methoxy-3-(4'-hydroxyphenyl) isocoumarin (IVc); 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl-4'-methoxyphenyl ketone (II d); 7-methoxy-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) isocoumarin (IVd); 7-methoxy-3-(4'-ethoxyphenyl) isocoumarin (IVe).

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Methoxyhomophthalic Anhydride (I), prepared by refluxing 4-methoxy-homophthalic acid² (5 g.) with acetic anhydride (10 ml.) for about 1 hr., was crystallised from acetic anhydride in needles (dried under reduced pressure at 120°, m.p. 144-45° (lit.³ m.p. same). (Found C, 62.7; H, 4.3. Calc. for C₁₀H₈O₄, C, 62.5; H, 4.2%).

Condensation of (I) with Aromatic compounds: (a) *In presence of Anhydrous AlCl₃*.—A mixture of the anhydride (I) (1 M), aromatic compound (1 M) and anhydrous AlCl₃ (1.5 M) in dry nitrobenzene was heated on a boiling water bath for 3 hrs. Crushed ice and HCl (conc.) were then added to the mixture and nitrobenzene (or the excess of the hydrocarbon as the case may be) was removed by steam distillation. The solid left was triturated with aq. NaHCO₃ repeatedly and filtered from the insoluble isocoumarin (IV). The filtrate, on acidification, precipitated the *o*-carboxybenzylphenyl ketone derivative (II). The products were crystallised from appropriate solvents (*vide* Table I)

(b) *In presence of Anhydrous SnCl₄*.—The anhydride (I) (1 M), aromatic compound (1 M), and anhydrous SnCl₄ (2 M) were mixed with shaking and heated in an oil bath at 120-25° for 2 hrs. Crushed ice and HCl (conc.) were added and the product separating, was refluxed with HCl (1 : 1) for about an hour and filtered. It was washed well with aq. NaHCO₃ and water and crystallised from appropriate solvent (*vide* Table I).

Cyclodehydration of the Ketones (II) with 85% H₂SO₄.—The ketone (II) (1 g.) was mixed with 85% H₂SO₄ (10 ml.) and left at the room temperature for 24 hrs. It was then poured on crushed ice. The product initially separating as paste, gradually solidified. After triturating with aq. NaHCO₃, it was crystallised from appropriate solvent (*vide* Table II)

TABLE II
Cyclodehydration of the ketones (II)

Ketone	Isocoumarin	Cryst. form and shape	M.P.	Found	Reqd.
(IIa)*	(IVa) C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₃	EtOH; fine needles	164-65°	C: 75.7% H: 5.1	76.1 4.8
(IIb)*	(IVb) C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃	Aq. ethanol; needles	179-80	C: 76.1 H: 5.1	76.6 5.2
(IIc)**	(IVc)*				
(IIId)**	(IVd)*				
(IIe)**	(IVe)*				

**Vide* Table I.

***Vide* Table III.

Alkaline Hydrolysis of the Isocoumarins (IV).—The isocoumarin (IV) (1 g.) was refluxed with aq. NaOH (10%; 12 ml.) for about 1 hr. and the resulting clear solution after cooling was treated with HCl. (conc.) The precipitated solid was dissolved in aq. NaHCO₃, filtered from traces of insoluble residue and acidified. The precipitate formed was crystallised from appropriate solvent (*vide* Table III).

Oxidation of Ketone (IIa).—Hydrogen peroxide (6 ml.; 100 vol.) was added portionwise to the solution of ketone (IIa) (0.5 g.) in aq. NaOH (5 ml.; 10%) and the mixture left

2. Desai and Usgaonkar, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 239.

3. Bose and Choudhary, *ibid.*, 1964, 41, 103.

overnight. It was warmed on a water-bath, cooled and acidified. The precipitated solid (m.p. 100-15°) was dried and sublimed at 100°/1 mm. and then at 160-70°/1mm. The first sublimate was purified by crystallisation from water and identified as *benzoic acid* by mixed m.p. method. The second sublimate was purified by resublimation. It had m.p. 96-97°, identified as *4-methoxyphthalic anhydride*. On dissolving it in aq. NaOH and reprecipitating by HCl, 4-methoxyphthalic acid was obtained; m.p. 169-70° (lit⁸ m.p. 169-70°)

TABLE III

Alkaline hydrolysis of the isocoumarins (IV)

Isocoumarin	Ketone	Cryst. form and shape.	M.P.		
(IVa)**	(IIa)*				
(IVb)**	(IIb)*				
(IVc)*	(IIc) C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃	EtOH; shining plates	237-38°	C: 67.1% H: 5.2	67.1% 4.9
(IVd)*	(II d)*				
(IVe)*	(Iie) C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃	Aq. ethanol; shining needles	202-03(d)	C: 69.0 H: 5.3	68.8 5.7

*Vide Table I.

**Vide Table II.

Oxidation of Ketone (IIb) was carried out in the same manner as described above. The dried product was repeatedly extracted with chloroform, the solvent evaporated and the residue crystallised from water to yield *p-toluic acid*, m.p. and mixed m.p. 177-78°. The chloroform-insoluble residue, after repeated crystallisation from water, had m.p. 169-70°, identified as *4-methoxyphthalic acid* by mixed m.p.

Oxidation of Ketone (IIc).—A mixture of ketone (IIc) (1 g.), KMnO₄ (3 g.) and aq. Na₂CO₃ (70 ml; 1%) was refluxed for 3 hrs., filtered hot, and the residue washed with boiling water. The filtrate and washings were concentrated to a small bulk and acidified with HCl. The sticky product formed was extracted with ether, the solvent removed, and the residue was sublimed at 160°/1 mm. The product was purified by resublimation and was identified as 4-methoxyphthalic anhydride, m.p. and mixed m.p. 96-97°. The residue, which did not sublime was dissolved in aq. NaHCO₃, filtered and acidified with HCl. The precipitated solid, on several crystallisations from water, gave the pure product, m.p. 212-13°, undepressed on admixture with a specimen of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid.

Oxidation of Ketone (II d) (1 g.) was carried out in the same manner as that of ketone (IIc). The product (m.p. 129-42°) was dried and sublimed at 130-40°/1 mm. and at 160°/1mm. The first sublimate, on resublimation, had m.p. 162-83° which was identified as *p-quinic acid* by mixed m.p. The other sublimate was identified as *4-methoxyphthalic anhydride*, m.p. and mixed m.p. 96-97°.

4. Bentley and Weizmann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 100.5. Cohen and Dudley, *ibid.*, 1910, 97, 1742.

Oxidation of Ketone (IIe) (1 g.) was carried out in the same manner as that of the ketone (IIc). The crude product was dried and sublimed at 160°/1mm to give *4-methoxyphthalic anhydride*. The residue was crystallised from sq. ethanol to afford *p-ethoxybenzoic acid*⁶, m.p. and mixed m.p. 195-97°.

The authors offer their thanks to Shri R. S. Kulkarni for the microanalyses.

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Received May 27, 1965.